

Project¹ Number: 824603
Project Acronym: ACTION
Project title: Participatory science toolkit against pollution

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

1. Data Summary

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The purpose of the data collection is to obtain information on water quality and water pollution events at Sado estuary in order to inform researchers and decision makers (from water sample analysis and historical information from the fishing community)

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

- 1) For water quality during the pilot, for each water sample the following parameters will be collected and uploaded into an excel file:
 - [data]
 - On the field:
 - Location (coordinate: lat + long)
 - Turbidity index (secchi depths) – Transparency (m)
 - Water temperature (°C)
 - Qualitative data (water appearance, colour, smell)
 - At the laboratory:
 - pH
 - Salinity (ppm)
 - Conductivity (mS/cm)
 - Ammonia (mg/L N)
 - Nitrate (mg/L)
 - Phosphate (mg/L PO4)
 - SST Suspended Solids (mg/L)
 - SOM Suspended organic matter (mg/L)
 - Pesticides exploratory screening (not made available on the public dataset)
 - [metadata]
 - Sample number
 - Date of collection
 - Hour of collection
 - Identification of the sample (location description)
 - Sampler ID code
 - Other observations
- 2) For historical information on water pollution events and sources:
 - a) On the field: >20 enquiries will be made with fishing community members; personal data will not be collected; relevant data about observed water pollution locations will be collected but not made public (observed pollution points, through identification on a map to generate GPS coordinates, qualitative aspects of water quality, temporal information about single or recurrent events and seasonality).

Will you re-use any existing data and how?

No

What is the origin of the data?

- 1) Water sample analysis: data will be obtained from samples collected by the participants and analyzed by the scientific partner "IPS"
- 2) Enquiries for historical data: data will be collected only by the Ocean Alive team in informal meetings with members of the community.

What is the expected size of the data?

We expect to analyse 20 water samples and to collect data through 1 enquiry to 20 members of the fishing community. The datasets will consist of excel, word and pdf generated files, estimated to up to 100 MB.

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

To researchers (for complementing current information on water quality on this estuary), the Portuguese agency for the environment; the companies, managers and decision-makers (to support management of the area and decisions).

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?

What naming conventions do you follow?

We will make data findable by using DOI from Zenodo.

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

Do you provide clear version numbers?

We will produce two datasets. The current data dataset will be available through Zenodo and will have a version number, using Zenodo tools. The historical data dataset won't be made public.

What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

- Date (and current Hour in case of water sampling)
- Collector's Id code
- Location (description)
- License
- Visibility
- Description
- Title

2.2. Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

We are now aiming to make openly available only the current dataset, by default, by the end of the pilot, on two platforms. Historical data dataset will not be available to the public due to participants' privacy protection. If during the data treatment we detect any constraints regarding sharing all current data collected (e.g. if high levels of pollution are detected and could compromise project participants safety or stakeholder engagement), we will discuss specific cases of constraints with ACTION consortium and project team, and evaluate restrictions to specific data.

Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if relevant provisions are made in the consortium agreement and are in line with the reasons for opting out.

Ok.

How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?

Data will be made accessible by deposition in two repositories: Zenodo and CoastNet (<http://geoportal.coastnet.pt/#>). Links to this repositories will be available in Ocean Alive's website.

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Data will be accessible to download with regular web browsers from Zenodo and our website, in common formats. Data will be also available through CoastNet geoportal in a .zip file (which includes .xls for data, .xml for metadata and .pdf for others).

Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No. There is available open software available to open and process .csv, .zip, .xls, .xml and .pdf data. On CoastNet geoportal there are a number of "help" buttons to guide the users to the data they need.

Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Not applicable

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.

For Zenodo: everything will be available in Zenodo

For website: we will use a link to Zenodo and/or Coastnet
For CoastNet: on a server in LNEC (National Laboratory for Civil Engineering)

During data collection and treatment data will be maintained in the NGO's OneDrive.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

No

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?

No restrictions will be used for the dataset uploaded on Zenodo, by default. Specific restrictions will be evaluated by when data is treated.

About CoastNet: Visualization of datasets are available through the geoportal and differentiated access permissions are supported.

Is there a need for a data access committee?

No.

Are there well described conditions for access (i.e. a machine readable license)?

Creative Commons licenses are both in human and machine readable versions. On CoastNet users have free access to data and data sources are identified and cited; also, there is a "read first" file and metadata in .pdf and .xml.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

We have no provision to identify persons using the data.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?

For the datasets published on Zenodo and our website, no as far as we know.

Datasets will be also available through web-based CoastNet platform; in the future they aim to be interoperable with Inspire Directive by the National System for Geographical Information (SNIG), and for that they are following recommendations from the national General-Directorate for the Territory (DGT).

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

For CoastNet: metadata files for historical data now available at the geoportal were created using GeMA software (Azores Metadata Manager <https://sma.idea.azores.gov.pt/>), by recommendation of the national General-Directorate for the Territory (DGT).

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?

We don't have information on this.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

We are not planning to use ontologies or vocabularies to describe the data generated.

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

We will attribute a creative commons license (CC BY 4.0) to the data.

When will the data be made available for reuse? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Data will be available for reuse by the end of the pilot (September 2021).

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

Data will be used by water pollution researchers to study changes on water quality over time and can be used as part of scientific outputs of related projects (scientific papers or reports). It will also be available to inform managers and decision-makers. However, it will be open to other environmental studies or commercial activities. There is not a restriction in the use of the data. We only nicely request to cite us using our DOI, and/or CoastNet infrastructure and funding.

[How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?](#)

Not defined.

[Are data quality assurance processes described?](#)

Not yet defined at this stage.

[Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address:](#)

3. Allocation of resources

[What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?](#)

The cost of making our data FAIR in public repositories like Zenodo is free. However, there is a cost to make data available through our website (hosting, web designer/programmer). For making data available on CoastNet we rely on CoastNet infrastructure and team, which has costs.

[How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant \(if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions\).](#)

During the pilot costs are attributed to the ACTION project budget. Afterwards, we are considering using Zenodo and CoastNet.

[Who will be responsible for data management in your project?](#)

The pilot's team.

[Are the resources for long term preservation discussed \(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long\)?](#)

Not yet defined at this stage.

4. Data security

[What provisions are in place for data security \(including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data\)?](#)

With the exception of data uploaded to public repositories, data is stored in the NGO's cloud (OneDrive for non profits) and hard drives, and scientific partners institutions repositories. Only personal authorized can access these data (secured by a user and password). Dataset of historical data will only be transferred to scientific partners with a non-disclosure agreement.

[Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?](#)

No

5. Ethical aspects

[Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action \(DoA\).](#)

Personal information about users will not be published in our public repositories. All personal information will be previously anonymized. If we detect any sensitive data (able to present safety issues on the project participants or raise legal questions with stakeholders) restrictions to the data sharing will be analysed with project partners and ACTION consortium before publishing. To assure participants privacy and also data quality, only the project team (Ocean Alive and IPS) will access the personal data (name and phone number) of participants. There are 6 people who can access participants personal data: Raquel Gaspar (OA), Sílvia Tavares (OA), Dina Galhanas (IPS), Ana Mata (IPS), Ricardo Salgado (IPS).

[Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?](#)

Published datasets will not contain personal data. Enquiries will be anonymized/pseudo-anonymised. GDPR consent forms will be prepared and delivered to the participants (including data sharing and long term preservation issues)

6. Other issues

Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?

None identified so far.

1The term 'project' used in this template equates to an 'action' in certain other Horizon 2020 doc